

COOLSCHOOLS Milestone MS6.1 (WP6):

Analysis of steps needed and constraints for developing the guidelines

PROJECT	COOLSCHOOLS – Realising Potentials of Nature-Based Climate Shelters in School Environments for Urban Transformations
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MILESTONE CONNECTED TO	Deliverable D6.1 “COOLSCHOOLS Guidelines for Schools with the Core Steps to Start the Process of Becoming a Climate Shelter”
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The COOLSCHOOLS Milestone MS6.1 under WP6 “Educational transformations”, is the analysis of the steps needed and constraints for developing the guidelines for schools on the core steps of designing a climate shelter. This Milestone was achieved on 29 January 2024, and we provide here an overview.

1. BACKGROUND:

One of the main tasks of the COOLSCHOOLS WP6 on educational transformations is to design guidelines for schools with the core steps to start the process of becoming a climate shelter (Task 6.1). This task, led by European Schoolnet with the support of WP leaders and Bruxelles Environment, will design guidelines on achieving transformations related to climate resilience, inclusiveness, enhanced well-being and learning opportunities and to overcoming residential disparities, based on the activities developed in the four sites organized in Barcelona, Brussels, Paris, and Rotterdam.

The initial step of the Guidelines’ design is to define the methodology to be followed and retrieve resources to support its creation, all the while assessing the constraints, both in terms of resources, scope, and human capacity.

2. METHODOLOGY:

2.1. DESIGNING THE GUIDELINES:

The first step of designing the Guidelines for schools is to define their objectives and their scope in relation to the content introduced in the document, and its target audience. In simple words, the team should decide the level of detail in the guidelines and determine the best framing of the information to ensure its relevance to the target audience(s).

Because the Guidelines will be designed for schools, it makes sense for them to address *school leadership* (heads of school, boards of direction, principals, or vice principals, head teachers, etc.). This choice is further mandated by the fact that the process of designing a green schoolyard will necessitate mobilising *funds and staff*, along with substantial *possible disruption in the use of the school playground*.

In terms of the practical steps relayed and explored in the guidelines, the focus of the guide will be on the planning and preparatory steps of the design process of a green schoolyard. Therefore, the guidelines will cover all steps from the inception of the idea of a climate shelter transformation to the final proposal for a climate shelter.

Because all subsequent steps will be unique to every situation, the latter implementation steps will not be included in the Guidelines, but instead, we will offer suggestions and guidance on the sustainability and maintenance of the green schoolyard, along with suggestion(s) on possible pedagogical uses for the green space in the long term.

It is essential that the guidelines be user friendly and offer easy navigation. Thus, the following tentative structure is currently being developed. The guidelines should give practical steps and information, using pragmatic, clear and concise language, supported by evidence.

- **Brief introduction** to the project and the methodology of the guidelines
- **Background.** What are climate shelters and what are their benefits? Why should school leaders endeavour to green their schoolyards? This will introduce the key health, cognitive and social benefits for students along with the ecosystem and biodiversity benefits for nature and animals. It will also introduce the potential benefits of climate shelters for local communities.
- **Practical steps for the planning of a green shelter, up to the writing of the final proposal for the green schoolyard.** This will include all relevant steps and stakeholders to include, means of utilising the process for pedagogical purposes, and some indication of the elements to consider when designing the green schoolyard. The steps will also include financial considerations, such as planning for and sourcing of the budget.
- **The possible challenges to creating a climate shelter.** Based on the testimonies of schools that have participated in the case studies, we will offer some general troubleshooting recommendations for schools.
- **The future of green shelters: use and maintenance.** This section will cover considerations for pedagogical activities and possible uses for climate shelters for learning purposes, in addition to some key consideration and advice for the maintenance of the green space in the long term.

2.2. SOURCES FOR CONTENT:

The next step in the preparation of the Guidelines includes retrieving key resources available to support their creation. The Guidelines will be based on the methodology of the case studies that have partnered with the COOLSCHOOLS project (<https://coolschools.eu/case-studies/>). The task is based on secondary research that will make use of all relevant published material by the case studies. This may include some practical guides, planning and implementation journal articles, interviews from participants who have engaged with climate shelters, etc.

Below are some examples of the resources collected to date:

- Paris: Planning steps, Oasis project, https://www.uia-initiative.eu/sites/default/files/2020-06/Paris_OASIS_Journal.pdf
- Paris: General guidelines for schools and decision makers <https://www.calameo.com/read/0040552785a1b08dc9eac?page=1>.
- Paris: How does it feel to be the Director of an OASIS School? Testimony from Paris Heads of School. <https://www.uia-initiative.eu/en/news/how-does-it-feel-be-director-oasis-school>
- Brussels: Participatory design process in *Opération Ré-création* <https://www.bubble.brussels/operation-re-creation-une-conception-participative/>
- Brussels : Urban partnerships and actors in *Opération Ré-création* <https://www.bubble.brussels/operation-re-creation-un-projet-multiple-aux-nombreux-partenaires/>
- Brussels: Steps and guides on implementing green spaces and activities within school and curriculum. <https://www.bubble.brussels/ressources/offre-pedagogique/>
- Barcelona: C40 cities guidelines on cooling schools https://www.barcelona.cat/barcelona-pel-clima/sites/default/files/documents/ccn_cooling_schools_city_case_studies.pdf
- Barcelona: Best practice report (EN pp 62-69) https://www.barcelona.cat/barcelona-pel-clima/sites/default/files/documents/informe_bp_refugis_climatics_v2_web.pdf
- Barcelona: final journal + lessons https://www.uia-initiative.eu/sites/default/files/2021-02/GBGAS2C_Barcelona_Journal%202.pdf
- Rotterdam: <https://www.groenblauweschoolpleinen.nl/aan-de-slag/>

In addition to the case study-specific material, the Guidelines will also make use of the research conducted as part of the project (as relevant) to emphasise the value of climate shelters for students. This may include the peer review articles published by the Consortium and the project deliverables.

2.3. CONSTRAINTS FOR DEVELOPING THE GUIDELINES:

The designing of guidelines for schools is a staple of European Schoolnet’s activities and therefore should follow a well-established process and comes with limited challenges and constraints.

Among the key limitations of the project, it is important to consider the necessity to use secondary research for producing the Guidelines, with limited opportunities to explore the details of the process in person with schools that have participated in the case studies. Indeed, the variety of experiences and contexts means that it will be more convenient, and adaptable, to base our Guidelines on the guiding documents that have been produced in the course of the climate shelter initiatives: case studies. Nevertheless, it also implies that we will be limited to the topics and steps that have been included in existing documents.

The purpose of our Guidelines, therefore, will be to synthesise the existing guides and create general guidance that will be of value for European schools. If topics arise that require further explanation, the team behind the Guidelines will endeavour to reach the case study partners for clarification.

The second key constraint in relation to the Guidelines connects to the misalignment with the Massive Open Online Course for teachers about the pedagogical value of climate shelters (another task of WP6). Indeed, while the initial timeline planned for the Guidelines to be delivered after the MOOC had concluded, it has become evident that there would be significant value in including the Guidelines for schools in the MOOC itself. This will not only give more visibility to the Guidelines but will also offer an additional instrument for the MOOC participants. Consequently, the deadline to produce the Guidelines will be moved up, so that they are ready prior to the launch of the MOOC on April 1, 2024. In essence, this will also enable us to align the approaches of the guidelines and the MOOC.

3. TIMELINE:

Table 1 below indicates the timeline for the creation of the Guidelines for schools in the form of Deliverable D6.1 “COOLSCHOOLS Guidelines”, including the link to the MOOC preparation and launch timeline. The timeline has been adapted to reflect the early submission of the Deliverable (note that the timeline may be subject to change to accommodate the needs of the project).

Month	Description
5 – 25 January 2024	Desktop research by EUN, planning of Deliverable D6.1 and drafting Milestone MS6.1
5 – 25 January 2024	EUN develops draft detailed Table of Contents (ToC) of Deliverable D6.1.
24 January 2024	Deadline for partners to share any resources relevant to the Deliverable D6.1
29 January – 2 February 2024	Partners review draft ToC, provide feedback as relevant
2 – 16 February 2024	EUN prepares full draft of Deliverable D6.1 + implements feedback from first review
16 – 22 February 2024	Final review by Lead Reviewer (other partners also welcome to review)
23 – 28 February 2024	EUN prepares final version of Deliverable D6.1
29 February 2024	Deliverable D6.1 submission
1 – 22 March 2024	Finalizing COOLSCHOOLS MOOC content, inclusion of Guidelines in content
1 April 2024	COOLSCHOOLS MOOC “Nature-Based Climate Shelters in Schools: Empowering Teachers for Sustainable Education” opens